

A Comprehensive Review of Weed Detection through Advanced Image Processing and Deep Learning

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Abstract

The agricultural industry now needs sustainable weed management techniques that are more effective than conventional pesticides. While these pesticides can be harmful to crops and the environment, weeds still pose a threat to these areas. However, the lack of efficient weed identification techniques makes it difficult to adopt new technologies that could provide targeted applications within crops. Fortunately, advanced methods for accurate weed control have been developed through smart farming practices. This paper examines the latest developments in image-based weed detection using deep learning algorithms. It will start with an overview of deep learning fundamentals related to weed detection, and then explore current developments in the field. This review paper examines the development of weed detection approaches. It explains the results of research on several topics, such as the identification of different types of weeds, image processing methods, and the application of various CNN (Convolutional Neural Networks) variations. This study provides insights into the Machine Learning (ML) and DL algorithms used to identify weeds or crops. The study concludes by reviewing the difficulties in developing workable weed identification techniques and discussing potential.

Keywords: Deep learning algorithms, Convolution Neural Networks, Machine Learning, Image Processing, Feature Extraction.

1. INTRODUCTION

Weed detection is the process of identifying and differentiating unwanted plants, also known as weeds, in a particular area, such as a garden or agricultural field. Weeds compete with crops for natural resources like nutrients, water, and sunlight, which can hurt agricultural productivity and quality. Traditional weed identification methods rely on manual labor, which can be time-consuming and labor-intensive. However, automated weed detection systems have been developed as a result of technological breakthroughs, particularly in the field of computer vision and machine learning. These systems take pictures of the agricultural landscape using cameras and drones, and advanced algorithms are then applied to process these images to identify and distinguish between weeds and crops based on visual clues. This method minimizes the need for excessive pesticide use and reduces its negative environmental impact, which not only improves the effectiveness of weed management but also supports sustainable agricultural practices.

2. GENERAL ARCHITECTURE OF WEED DETECTION USING IMAGE PROCESSING AND DEEP LEARNING

When detecting weeds, it is important to follow several steps. Here is a summary of the general procedure:

2.1 Image Acquisition

High-resolution photos of the agricultural field need to be obtained using various imaging systems such as satellites, drones, and ground-based vehicles. It is important to ensure uniform coverage and image quality in all areas.

2.2 Data Preprocessing

The quality of the data can be improved by using image preprocessing methods such as scaling photographs to a uniform resolution for consistency in later processing stages, applying filters for noise reduction, and adjusting brightness and contrast.

2.3 Segmentation

The photos need to be divided into separate regions that represent various objects using image segmentation techniques. This process isolates the crop from possible weed regions to detect weeds. Methods like thresholding, clustering, or deep learning-based semantic segmentation (e.g., U-Net) can be used.

2.4 Feature Extraction

Pertinent features need to be extracted from the divided regions. For instance, texture features, color histograms, or form descriptors can be used to describe the look of both crops and weeds. These characteristics are used as inputs for the next stage of classification.

2.5 Dataset Creation

The photos need to be annotated to generate a labeled dataset for training and assessment. Areas of interest, like the edges of weeds and crops, need to be marked and given the appropriate class labels.

2.6 Selecting A Model

A model that is appropriate for the task of weed detection needs to be selected. Convolutional neural networks (CNNs) are frequently employed for image-based tasks since they can automatically learn hierarchical features. This is notably the case for architectures like ResNet, VGG, or EfficientNet.

2.7 Transfer Learning (Optional)

Pre-trained models on large datasets can be used to start the model with important features gained from similar tasks. To make the model more suitable for the target domain, it can be fine-tuned using the particular weed identification dataset.

2.8 Training

The annotated dataset is used to train the selected model. An optimization approach, such as stochastic gradient descent, is used to reduce the discrepancy between the expected and actual labels. As necessary, batch sizes and learning rates can be adjusted.

Fig 1: Block Diagram of General steps of weed detection

2.9 Validation

The trained model's generalization ability is gauged by testing it on a different validation dataset. The model's efficacy is analyzed using metrics like accuracy, precision, recall, and F1 score. If the model shows signs of underfitting or overfitting, hyperparameters need to be adjusted.

2.10 Testing and Inference

The trained model's performance is evaluated on a separate testing dataset to ensure accuracy in real-world situations. It can be applied to fresh, unviewed photos for weed detection in both controlled testing settings and real-world agricultural fields.

2.11 post-processing

Post-processing techniques can be applied to improve the model's predictions. This could involve morphological procedures for better weed boundary localization, thresholding to weed out low-confidence predictions, and non-maximum suppression to get rid of redundant detections.

2.12 Integration

The trained model is integrated into the target application, such as agricultural equipment that has cameras, to detect weeds in real-time. Smooth communication between the agricultural automation framework and the detecting system needs to be ensured.

2.13 Continuous Monitoring and Improvement

The model's performance in practical applications needs to be monitored. Further annotated data can be gathered, and the model can be retrained to adjust and increase its accuracy over time as performance deteriorates or new difficulties arise.

3. VARIOUS WEED DETECTION APPROACHES USING IMAGE PROCESSING AND DEEP LEARNING

Accurately identifying weed species is one of the main obstacles to automated and precise weeding. [1]. Deep learning approaches and traditional image processing techniques are the two main categories into which computer vision solutions for field weed detection may be generally classified. In classic image processing, characteristics like color, texture, and form are extracted from photos and used with conventional machine learning methods like Support Vector Machine (SVM) or random forest to identify weeds. These methods, however, rely largely on the picture capture and pre-processing methods employed, as well as the success of feature extraction, and necessitate human feature extraction. The review by Zhangnan Wu et al [2] covers the standard image-processing and deep-learning approaches to weed detection. It summarizes modern methods, evaluates the pros and cons of each, highlights relevant datasets and equipment, and identifies current issues. The review concludes by discussing potential avenues for future research and emerging trends in weed detection. The use of machine learning in agriculture has been thoroughly explored in various reviews, such as that by Yangkai Zhang et al [3]. Additionally, a comprehensive overview focusing on the application of deep learning techniques to different farming activities is available.

Ildar Rakhmatuulin et al [4] study examines the impact of deep learning on agricultural weed identification, with a focus on cutting-edge technologies. The discussion provides a brief overview of the development and application of these technologies in weed detection. The systematic review investigates AI-based weed detection systems, with a particular emphasis on current developments in deep learning (DL). The paper examines several deep-learning techniques and analyzes their effectiveness, usefulness, and potential for weed identification. The authors highlight a few limitations that hinder the widespread use of Artificial intelligence and Deep Learning in commercial applications. Kun Hu et al [5] study offers a comprehensive analysis of the latest advancements in identifying weeds through deep-learning techniques in images. The review begins by introducing the fundamental concepts of deep learning in the context of weed detection. It then explores the most recent developments in this field, while considering relevant research resources such as openly accessible datasets with a cannabis theme. The report concludes by outlining the challenges encountered in creating effective weed identification techniques and suggesting future research directions. [6] study accurately identifies weeds; it is important to utilize a variety of data collection methods. This can involve using robotics, multiple cameras, and optimal deep-learning algorithms. It is also crucial to have sizable and well-balanced datasets that include a range of sensors for real-world scenarios. The study addresses the difficulties, technical paths, and annotation techniques for deep learning-based weed recognition. It investigates the efficacy of models such as CNN and GAN and proposes use cases for them in the production of artificial training data. Overall, the paper highlights the advancements and possibilities of deep learning for weed identification in precision agriculture, while also identifying obstacles and suggesting avenues for future research.

The agricultural industry is transforming due to the introduction of innovative weed identification techniques that use advanced technologies to address problems caused by unwanted plant growth. These techniques act as vigilant protectors for farmers by utilizing intricate color, form, and texture analyses using computer vision to distinguish between crops and weeds. Deep learning algorithms interpret complex patterns with the accuracy of eagle eyes. Sensor-based techniques such as fluorescence and optical sensors accurately detect slight variations in light reflectance or chlorophyll, whereas spectral imaging uses infrared and thermal wavelengths to identify weeds that are difficult to spot. The Internet of Things (IoT) makes it easier to integrate this diverse data, creating a seamless, real-time intelligence

network that allows for ongoing weed monitoring. The choice of the best approach depends on the specific situation. To enable the advancement of weed identification technologies for efficient agricultural weed control, a variety of publicly available image datasets in computer vision are accessible to researchers and practitioners.

3.1 Methods for The Identification of Weeds Using Deep Learning

M. Vaidhehi et al [7] This paper proposes a deep learning model for accurately segmenting weeds in paddy fields. The model uses Regional Convolutional Neural Networks (R-CNN) and real-time data from agricultural regions to emphasize the importance of weed removal. The R-CNN model uses a specific architecture for determining the bounding box and deep convolutional layers for extracting features. The process includes preprocessing, segmentation, and dataset collection. The performance evaluation shows an accuracy of 83.33%, which is better than current methods. However, certain limitations need to be addressed, and more research is required in this area to improve weed growth prediction, crop-weed discrimination, and detection techniques.

Jialin Yu et al [8] This research delves into the use of VGGNet and DetectNet, two types of deep convolutional neural networks (DCNNs), for precise weed management in perennial ryegrass. VGGNet was found to be highly effective, achieving notable recall and F1 scores in identifying specific weed species. The researchers employed a combination of object detection DCNN and single- and multiple-species neural networks for training. They evaluated the results using metrics such as Matthew's correlation coefficient (MCC), recall, precision, and F1 score. The study also explored the integration of DCNN in smart sprayer machine vision systems for object identification and categorization. However, the study was limited by an uneven training dataset, a small geographic training image set, and the need for a larger and more diverse training dataset. The report also highlighted research gaps, including the need for larger neural networks to cover a wider range of weed species, exploration of the effect of the ratio of negative to positive images on neural network performance, the limited geographical diversity in the current training dataset, and the potential benefits of pixel-wise semantic segmentation for accuracy improvement. The authors also noted that there were no business or financial ties.

Xiaojun Jin et al [9] The main goal of this research is to develop a reliable robotic system for removing weeds from vegetable farms using deep learning and image processing. The proposed solution utilizes color index-based segmentation for weed removal and a trained CenterNet model for vegetable detection. This solution has achieved a 0.953% F1 score a recall of 95.0%, and a precision of 95.6%. Color index segmentation is more efficient and less computationally demanding than ExG index segmentation. However, the research has identified several limitations, such as the need for further investigation into plant identification in in-situ recordings, and the algorithm's inability to detect certain weed species due to occlusion. The model's estimated accuracy rate is 95%. The study has highlighted some gaps in the literature, such as the lack of prior research on weed identification in vegetable plantations, the challenges of dealing with weed mixing and random plant spacing during harvesting, the necessity for a visual weed identification method for sustainable management, and the potential use of robotic weeding. However, the algorithm is not suitable for organic vegetables and does not account for the adverse effects of excessive chemical herbicide use on the ecosystem.

A. Subeesh et al [10] A study was conducted to assess how effectively deep learning techniques could identify weeds in bell pepper fields, to improve weed control precision and automate agricultural processes. The study found that the InceptionV3 model outperformed other models, such as Alexnet, GoogLeNet, and Xception when analyzing RGB photos from a playhouse. The research involved gathering data, preprocessing, augmenting data, and building training, testing, and validation sets. The model's performance was evaluated using accuracy, precision, and recall metrics. InceptionV3 achieved an impressive 97.7% accuracy after 30 epochs and 16 batches. The study identified research gaps and emphasized the need for further investigation and development of automation and digitization methods for weed identification in farming environments. It also suggested that improvements in deep learning models could enhance the effectiveness and precision of weed identification. Although the study did not specify particular research gaps, it called for more research and development in these areas.

Yerragudipadu Subbarayudu et al [11] study suggests that the use of deep learning and image processing can help maximize crop yields and minimize the need for pesticides in agriculture. Early detection of weeds is crucial, and machine learning can be used to predict crop fertilizer requirements, thereby increasing fertilizer efficiency in farming. The procedure involves collecting images, pre-processing them, and using a two-stage deep learning method for weed detection, which produces a model that can predict crop classifications with 90% accuracy. The suggested procedures have shown high accuracy values for weed identification (97.5%), fertilizer recommendation (90.6%), and crop class prediction (92.68%). However, the study also points out some challenges, such as the lack of standardized data collection methods, the need for timely and reliable data, and the requirement for interpretable models. The study offers insights into future research possibilities in this field.

Faiza Khan et al [12] study aimed to use computer vision and artificial intelligence to accurately identify weeds in potato crops. The researchers utilized a dataset comprising five different types of potato weeds to predict site-specific spraying in potato fields, leading to effective weed management. They collected several species of potato weeds from various environmental and climatic settings as part of their approach. The Tiny-YOLOv4 model was trained on this dataset and achieved a mean average precision (mAP) value of 49.4%. For the highest accuracy in real-time potato weed detection, the top-performing model weights were used. However, the study acknowledges some limitations, such as the unavailability of the picture dataset for public access, modest testing accuracy on a limited dataset, and the need for further development and refinement to improve detection accuracy overall. The paper also highlights several issues, including the lack of a publicly available image dataset for potato weeds and the critical need for system expansion and improvement, particularly regarding site-specific spraying technology to achieve higher detection accuracy. In conclusion, the article uses deep learning approaches to enhance weed identification in potato crops. However, it also suggests directions for additional study and system enhancement while acknowledging current shortcomings.

Ch. Lakshmi Narayana et al [13] study shows the importance of YOLOv7 in agriculture is highlighted in this research, which presents an effective real-time weed detection method. The paper notes that YOLOv7 has limitations, especially in correctly identifying small or occluded weeds and probable misclassifications, despite having superior mean average precision (mAP) in the early crop weed dataset (99.6) and the 4weed dataset (78.53). The methodology includes cloud-based resources, model training, and the proposal and implementation of an object identification strategy based on YOLOv7. Recommendations for larger datasets, better model training, and data augmentation are made in light of the limitations that have been found, which include a restricted dataset that affects accuracy and generalizability. Emphasizing the significance of field experiments for real-world assessment, research gaps highlight the need for larger and diversified datasets, more stability in weed identification, and additional investigations for greater detection accuracy.

Urmashv et al [14] research is focused on developing a neural network, YOLOv5, equipped with an attention module and classical algorithms for weed detection in agriculture. The aim is to successfully classify low-resolution weed photos by creating a proprietary database that includes over 1000 photographs for each type of weed. The process involves examining various regions, collecting training data, improving the YOLOv5 architecture, and assessing efficacy through evaluation measures. While the weed recognition accuracy percentage varied across classifiers such as K-Nearest Neighbors, Random Forest, and Decision Tree, the YOLOv5 architecture showed promising results. However, the study is limited by a small amount of training data, the need for powerful computers, and lower mean precision in comparisons. Future research should focus on weed diversity and geography, practical agricultural applications, optimizing YOLOv5, and the dataset's usefulness for other researchers.

Zichao Jiang's [15] research project utilized Keras-implemented VGG16 transfer learning to detect twelve different types of weeds in the field, achieving an impressive 98.99% accuracy on the training set and 91.08% accuracy on the verification set. The researchers used VGG16 with fixed layers for feature extraction and added additional layers for classification. The study focused on practical applications in pesticide application and agricultural weed identification. However, it had some limitations such as an inadequate design and a restricted concentration on useful technology research. Therefore, the research suggests the need for improvements by collecting more diverse weed photos. Research gaps point to the need for more complete design features, manual features based on agricultural knowledge, greater practical technology research, and advancements in practical applications to handle a larger range of weeds.

Paidi Sravanthi et al [16] A recent study highlights the significance of agriculture in the Indian economy and discusses the challenges caused by invasive weeds. The study proposes a unique approach for detecting and preventing weeds that employs deep learning and image processing. The approach uses a dataset from Kaggle that includes images of different weeds and sesame crops. It combines Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) with the YOLO framework and includes unsupervised learning as labeling data is limited. The YOLO-WEED system effectively predicts agricultural production and is suitable for real-time weed detection through Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs). The accuracy range of weed classification is between 70.3% to 82.3%, demonstrating the superiority of DL-based CNN over conventional techniques. However, the need for comprehensive labeling data, unproven methods for weeds associated with crops, and possible dataset constraints are among the limitations. More research is needed to understand how robotics and artificial intelligence affect agricultural weed detection and to consider dataset generalizability.

Bishwa B Sapkota et al [17] study emphasizes the importance of targeting weeds based on their specific locations and introduces a new technique for identifying weeds using artificial images. The research shows that synthetic images generated from Generative Adversarial Networks (GAN) are not effective. The study also investigates the ideal number of plant samples and the advantages of crop row orientation. The study finds that manually and automatically cropped plant instances perform similarly. The Mask R-CNN model achieves an accuracy of 0.60 to 0.83 using synthetic images, while real plant-based synthetic images achieve an accuracy of 80% when compared to authentic photos. Interestingly,

there is no noticeable improvement in performance when blending synthetic and real photographs. The limitations of this study include the need for further investigation on a range of weed densities and growth phases, as well as difficulties with automatic cropping and practical use. The study suggests the need for improved GAN-derived synthetic images, advanced synthetic image-generating techniques, and deeper research in this field.

Tavseef Mairaj Shah et al [18] study focuses on using artificial neural networks to identify plants and weeds in agriculture, particularly through a robot. The research investigates the application of data augmentation to improve the accuracy of the identification process, the use of transfer learning strategies, and the importance of hyperparameter tweaking. The study highlights the potential benefits of unmanned aircraft systems and neural networks for sustainable farming practices and maximizing yield and profits for farmers. However, the study reveals gaps in the research, such as the need for a larger and more diverse dataset, real-world testing, integration with complementary technologies, and a comprehensive assessment of cost-effectiveness, especially for small-scale farmers. To enhance the efficiency and usefulness of the plant and weed identification robot, these gaps must be addressed. In summary, the study emphasizes the importance of artificial neural networks in picture identification for agroecology and the need to fill the gaps in the research to improve the plant and weed identifier robot.

Lijo Jacob et al [19] The research being discussed focuses on the use of Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) for identifying diseases and weeds in Indian fields. The study highlights the crucial role of accurate disease detection in aiding farmers and agricultural advisors. The paper emphasizes how technology can help overcome obstacles in agriculture by providing accurate information and recommending appropriate herbicides. The methodology takes a holistic approach, utilizing machine learning, neural networks, and image processing techniques. It includes pre-processing, segmentation, feature extraction, image capture, and classification, with two separate stages for training and testing data. The system offers real-time crop, disease, and weed diagnosis while recommending suitable agricultural actions. It does this by using color and texture cues for image processing. The suggested system aims to improve the overall quality and production processes of agricultural fields by detecting both major and minor diseases and offering real-time identification based on various characteristics and species. It recognizes the limitations of current systems, which lack real-time results and focus solely on crop diseases.

Tao Tao et al [20] This study explores the development of a hybrid CNN-SVM classifier called the VGG-SVM model. The goal of this model is to identify weeds in winter rape fields automatically. The results show that the VGG-SVM model is a highly effective tool for weed identification, with excellent classification accuracy and real-time performance. The paper includes a comparative experiment and validation under varying illumination conditions. It also highlights the potential usefulness of the VGG-SVM model for identifying different crops and weeds in agricultural fields. The researchers conducted training and testing experiments using a dataset of rape sowing and weeds, examining the effect of network parameters on performance. The methodology involves building a feature extraction network based on VGG Net. Despite the positive aspects of the study, the authors point out research needs, such as the lack of effective illumination condition labeling in the dataset, which limits its realism. Additionally, further research is needed to expand the use of the VGG-SVM model to recognize multi-sample mixed crop photos in a variety of field situations, as there is still a concentration on single winter rape categorization.

4. PROPOSED METHOD FOR DATASET CREATION

A new system for categorizing weeds based on image processing and machine learning has been proposed to meet the increased demand for sustainable weed management in agriculture. The method starts by collecting high-resolution photos from agricultural fields to ensure a thorough representation of various weed species and environmental conditions. These photos undergo preprocessing procedures to enhance their quality and facilitate feature extraction. Important features, such as texture descriptors and color histograms, are extracted to serve as informative features for the machine learning model. The sample image of the weed data set is shown in Figure 2

Figure 2: Sample Data Collected From field

A Support Vector Machine (SVM) is chosen, and a meticulously labeled dataset is used to train the model to identify patterns and relationships crucial for precise weed classification and Compared with Random Forest classifier Boost and KNN. The model's robust performance is confirmed through rigorous validation procedures, ensuring its adaptability to new, unseen data. The proposed system integrates seamlessly with smart farming practices, enabling real-time decision-making in precision agriculture. The system's potential to reduce reliance on conventional herbicides highlights its environmental impact, promoting more sustainable farming practices. Continuous improvement strategies ensure the model's ongoing evolution, including its ability to adapt to changing weed species and evolving agricultural landscapes. This comprehensive methodology represents a significant advancement in developing efficient, technology-driven, and environmentally conscious weed management techniques in contemporary agriculture.

CONCLUSION

This review covers the important progress made in weed recognition methods and the challenges and untapped potential. The study highlights the need for multidisciplinary approaches to weed recognition, which have been developed across various study disciplines. The selection of recognition algorithms is a critical consideration, taking into account precision requirements, occlusion issues, and in-field weed control treatment scenarios. The study stresses the importance of extensive datasets with different situations, which are essential for the efficient identification of weeds in real-world applications. The conclusion emphasizes the need for large datasets to further advance this research field and recognizes the growing interest in deep learning-based weed recognition from various research communities. In summary, the review outlines the progress, difficulties, and opportunities in the field of weed detection through advanced image processing and deep learning.

REFERENCES

1. Yecheng Wang, Shuangqing Zhang, Baisheng Dai (2023) Fine-grained weed recognition using Swin Transformer and two-stage transfer learning in Sustainable and Intelligent Phytoprotection, a section of the journal *Frontiers in Plant Science*
2. Zhangnan Wu, Yajun Chen, Bo Zhao, Xiaobing Kang, and Yuanyuan Ding (2021) Review of Weed Detection Methods Based on Computer Vision in *Sensors* 2021 (MDPI) 21,3647. <https://doi.org/10.3390/s21113647>
3. Yangkai Zhang, Mengke Wang, Danlei Zhao, Chunye Liu, Zhengguang Liu Early weed identification based on deep learning: A review *Smart Agricultural Technology* 3 (2023) 100123 Published by Elsevier
4. Ildar Rakhmatulin, Andreas Kamilaris, and Christian Andreassen Deep Neural Networks to Detect Weeds from Crops in Agricultural Environments in Real-Time: A Review *Remote Sensing*. 2021, 13, 4486. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs13214486>
5. Kun Hu, Zhiyong Wang, Guy Coleman, Asher Bender, Tingting Yao, Shan Zeng, Dezhen Song, Arnold Schumann, Michael Walsh Deep learning techniques for in-crop weed recognition in large-scale grain production systems: a review in *Precision Agric* (2023) published in Springer. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11119-023-10073-1>
6. Wenze Hu, Samuel Oliver Wane, Junke Zhu, Dongsheng Li, Qing Zhang, Xiaoting Bie, Yubin Lan Review of deep learning-based weed identification in crop fields in *Int J Agric & Biol Eng* Vol. 16 No. 4 July 2023.
7. M. Vaidhehi & C. Malathy An unique model for weed and paddy detection using regional convolutional neural networks *Acta Agriculturae Scandinavica, Section B — Soil & Plant Science*, 72:1, 463-475, DOI: 10.1080/09064710.2021.2011395.
8. Jialin Yu, Arnold W. Schumann, Zhe Cao, Shaun M. Sharpe, and Nathan S. Boyd Sharpe SM and Boyd NS (2019) Weed Detection in Perennial Ryegrass With Deep Learning Convolutional Neural Network. *Front. Plant Sci.* 10:1422. doi: 10.3389/fpls.2019.01422
9. Xiaojun Jin, Jun Che, And Yong Chen Weed Identification Using Deep Learning and Image Processing in Vegetable Plantation *IEEE Access* (Volume: 9) 10.1109/ACCESS.2021.3050296
10. A. Subeesh, S. Bhole, K. Singh, N.S. Chandel, Y.A. Rajwade, K.V.R. Rao, S.P. Kumar, D. Jat Deep convolutional neural network models for weed detection in polyhouse grown bell peppers *Artificial Intelligence in Agriculture* Volume 6, 2022, Pages 47-54.
11. Yerragudipadu Subbarayudu, Adithi Soppadand, Shreya Vyamasan and Supriya Bandanadam The Distributed Deep Learning Paradigms for Detection of Weeds from Crops in Indian Agricultural Farms *E3S Web of Conferences* 391, 01057 (2023) *ICMED-ICMPC 2023* <https://doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/202339101057>
12. Faiza Khan, Noureen Zafar, Muhammad Naveed Tahir, Muhammad Aqib, Shoaib Saleem, and Zainab Haroon Deep Learning-Based Approach for Weed Detection in Potato Crops *Environ. Sci. Proc.* 2022, 23, 6. <https://doi.org/10.3390/environsciproc2022023006>
13. Ch. Lakshmi Narayana, Kondapall Venkata Ramana An Efficient Real-Time Weed Detection Technique using YOLOv7 (IJACSA) *International Journal of Advanced Computer Science and Applications*, Vol. 14, No. 2, 2023
14. Urmashv, B., Buribayev, Z., Amirgalieva, Z., Ataniyazova, A., Zhassuzak, M., Turegali, A. (2021). Development of a weed detection system using machine learning and neural network algorithms. *Eastern-European Journal of Enterprise Technologies*, 6 (2 (114)), 70–85. doi: <https://doi.org/10.15587/1729-4061.2021.246706>

15. Zichao Jiang A Novel Crop Weed Recognition Method Based on Transfer Learning from VGG16 Implemented by Keras IOP Conf. Series: Materials Science and Engineering 677 (2019) 032073 IOP Publishing doi:10.1088/1757-899X/677/3/032073
16. Paidi Sravanthi, Dr. Kunjam Nageswara Rao, Dr. G. Sita Ratnam, P. Mohan Rao Weed Detection using CNN and YOLO framework Journal of Engineering Sciences Vol 13 Issue 09,2022, ISSN:0377-9254
17. Bishwa B Sapkota, Sorin Popescu, Nithya Rajan, Ramon G Leon, Chris Reberg-Horton, Steven Mirsky, V Muthukumar, Bagavathiannan Use of synthetic images for training a deep learning model for weed detection and biomass estimation in cotton Scientific Reports | (2022) 12:19580 | <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-022-23399-z>
18. Tavseef Mairaj Shah, Durga Prasad Babu Nasika and Ralf Otterpohl Plant and Weed Identifier Robot as an Agroecological Tool Using Artificial Neural Networks for Image Identification Agriculture 2021, 11, 222. <https://doi.org/10.3390/agriculture11030222>
19. Lijo Jacob¹, Aishwarya Patil², Karishma Patil³, K.S. Charumathi Weed Detection In Indian Fields And Disease Detection Using Convolutional Neural Network International Research Journal of Engineering and Technology (IRJET) e-ISSN: 2395-0056 Volume: 08 Issue: 05 | May 2021 www.irjet.net p-ISSN: 2395-0072
20. Tao, T., Wei, X. A hybrid CNN–SVM classifier for weed recognition in winter rape field. Plant Methods 18, 29 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13007-022-00869-z>.
21. Mu Y, Ni R, Fu L, Luo T, Feng R, Li J, Pan H, Wang Y, Sun Y, Gong H, Guo Y, Hu T, Bao Y and Li S (2023) DenseNet weed recognition model combining local variance preprocessing and attention mechanism. Front. Plant Sci. 13:1041510. doi: 10.3389/fpls.2022.1041510
22. Wang Y, Zhang S, Dai B, Yang S and Song H (2023) Fine-grained weed recognition using Swin Transformer and two-stage transfer learning. Front. Plant Sci. 14:1134932. doi: 10.3389/fpls.2023.1134932
23. Uchechukwu Ngozi Nwachukwu, Cristian Rodriguez Rivero Weed Recognition in Sesame Field Using Computer Vision Algorithms 2022 International Conference on Computational Science and Computational Intelligence (CSCI) 979-8-3503-2028-2/22/\$31.00 ©2022 IEEE DOI 10.1109/CSCI58124.2022.00304
24. Saleem MH, Velayudhan KK, Potgieter J and Arif KM (2022) Weed Identification by Single-Stage and Two-Stage Neural Networks: A Study on the Impact of Image Resizers and Weights Optimization Algorithms. Front. Plant Sci. 13:850666. doi: 10.3389/fpls.2022.850666
25. Zhang, H., Wang, Z.; Guo, Y., Ma, Y.; Cao, W., Chen, D.; Yang, S.; Gao, R. Weed Detection in Peanut Fields Based on Machine Vision. Agriculture2022,12,1541. <https://doi.org/10.3390/agriculture12101541>
26. Yang, Yana; Li, Yang; Yang, Jiachen; And Wen, Jiabao (2022) "Dissimilarity-based active learning for embedded weed identification," Turkish Journal of Agriculture and Forestry: Vol. 46: No. 3, Article 11. <https://doi.org/10.55730/1300-011X.3011>.
27. Luis O. López, Gloria Ortega, Francisco Agüera-Vega, Fernando Carvajal-Ramírez, Patricio Martínez-Carricondo, Ester M. Garzón Multi-Spectral Imaging for Weed Identification in Herbicides Testing INFORMATICA, 2022, Vol.No.4,71–793 771 © 2022 Vilnius University DOI: <https://doi.org/10.15388/22-INFOR498>
28. R. Kingsy Grace, J. Anitha, R. Sivaramakrishnan, and M.S.S. Sivakumar Crop and Weed Classification Using Deep Learning Turkish Journal of Computer and Mathematics Education Vol.12 No.7 (2021),935-938
29. Gerassimos G. Peteinatos, Philipp Reichel, Jeremy Karouta, Dionisio Andújar and Roland Gerhards Weed Identification in Maize, Sunflower, and Potatoes with the Aid of Convolutional Neural Networks Remote Sens. 2020, 12, 4185; doi:10.3390/rs12244185
30. Saha, Dheeman, Development of Enhanced Weed Detection System with Adaptive Thresholding, K-Means and Support Vector Machine (2019). Electronic Theses and Dissertations. 3374. <https://openprairie.sdstate.edu/etd/3374>